

Optimization of Passive Residential Exhaust systems through Airfoil-Assisted Venturi Effect Integration

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Abstract

Traditional passive exhaust systems (chimneys) , although efficient, suffer from backflow, insufficient air exhaust due to turbulent air flow mechanism. This research aims in creating a highly efficient ventilation system without the use of mechanical energy by integrating airfoil geometry which utilizes venturi effect. Through an iterative process, compared with a traditional chimney showed an 18% decrease in smoke clearance time and successfully eliminated backflow. Demonstrating efficiency of aerospace engineering principles in residential systems.

I. Introduction

Conventional chimneys facilitate air exchange through stack ventilation effect(Above All,2026) as illustrated in figure 1 below

Figure 1: Illustration of heat loss and pressure differentials caused by the stack effect in homes. Source: (Above All, 2026).

eliminating the need for mechanical energy; however they often exhibit turbulent airflow due to boundary layer

separation. This study hypothesises the efficiency of an airfoil integrated into the conventional model which creates a pressure differential that helps air exchange via Bernoulli's principle and Venturi effect. By stabilizing airflow this modification aims to prevent backflow and increase the efficiency of the conventional model by a margin

II. Materials and Methods

The experimental apparatus consisted of a scale "mock house" constructed from a cardboard box featuring a window covered with cling wrap to observe the behaviour of smoke within the chamber. A circular aperture was cut at the top of the box to drive as an attachment point for a cardboard tube which functioned as the chimney.

Figure 2: Preparation of the mock residential chamber. The box was modified to create an airtight seal, ensuring that the only airflow path within the system was through the experimental chimney assembly. Source : (Author, 2026)

To simulate natural environmental conditions a hairdryer with optimized speed settings was utilized to emulate a consistent, slight breeze.

Smoke was generated through the controlled combustion of benzoin resin which produced a clean white smoke optimized for visual observation. During testing, the smoke was allowed to fill the apparatus until the chamber reached a state of saturation. The air exchange behaviour was then monitored and recorded for both the conventional exhaust and of the prototype created. To ensure experimental consistency, all testing conditions were maintained at identical settings for both configurations

III. Design Iterations

To reach the final design, an iterative testing process was employed:

Iteration 01:

A cardboard airfoil was installed within the internal exhaust channel, intended to generate suction forces on both sides of the structure. Testing revealed that the symmetric positioning of the airfoil caused the opposing force vectors to cancel each other out. Rather than facilitating airflow, the internal geometry acted as a flow obstruction, resulting in a performance decline compared to the conventional model

Figure 3: conceptual planning and notes for prototype 1, which failed due to the symmetric positioning of the airfoil placement, identifying a design limitation. Source : (Author, 2026)

Figure 4: Detailed notes for prototype 01 illustrating why the prototype failed (Author,2026)

Iteration 02: In this prototype the airfoil was shifted to an external position to harness wind energy. An airfoil made out of thick paper was mounted over the chimney outlet, maintained at a fixed elevation above the exhaust. As external wind flows along the curved surface. It generates a low pressure zone at the chimney exit via the venturi effect and Bernoulli's principle (Pilot Mail,2026) This pressure differential creates a strong suction force that actively pulls out air, preventing backflow and optimizing exhaust efficiency.

Figure 5: Prototype 2. The aerodynamic curvature is designed to optimize airflow at the exhaust outlet. Source : (Author,2026)

IV. Results

Both prototypes from iteration 01 and iterations 02 were tested against the standard model. The data and observations from iteration 02 are listed below.

Metric	Standard	Iteration 02
Smoke clearance time	Baseline (T + 0)	27 seconds faster (T - 27)
Airflow pattern	Turbulent	Laminar
Backflow observation	Frequent	None
Environmental shielding	Minimal	High

(Table 01 : Comparative analysis of exhaust efficiency)

Refinement notes : To ensure testing accuracy. The interior of the mock chamber was rendered in black to improve visibility of the white smoke. All structural joints were sealed with hot glue to prevent air leakage.

Below contain the footage of the conventional model's exhaust power compared to prototype 2

The above listed data indicated a clear performance improvement in the optimized model. While the standard chimney relied solely on passive stack effect, often hindered by turbulence. The integration of an airfoil Improved performance by a margin and eliminated major concerns like backflow of air and environmental protection. The data above confirms the design's effectiveness.

Figure 6: Final iteration of the experiment, with the mock house and the optimized external airfoil assembly. Source (Author, 2026)

V. Discussion

The quantitative and qualitative results confirm that the optimized airfoil integrated design significantly outperforms the conventional model.

The performance deficit of the conventional design can be attributed to its reliance on a passive non optimized

stack effect – A buoyancy- driven process where warm less dense air rises and exits through the top of the structure. While it is reliable and cost effective it comes with several drawbacks such as backflow and boundary layer separation.

As air moves upwards, it detaches from the surface, creating turbulent pockets that act as a mechanical brake on the system This turbulence is the primary cause of sluggish backflow observed.

In the prototype created, The stack effect (Above All,2026)is optimized, by positioning the airfoil above the exhaust. We leverage Bernoulli’s principle (Figure 7) and the venturi effect(Figure 8)

Figure 7: Illustration of Bernoulli's Principle, which states that as the speed of a fluid increases, its pressure decreases. Source: Pilot Mall (2026).

Figure 8:The Venturi Effect, occurring when fluid speeds up within a narrow passage, resulting in a drop in pressure. Source: Pilot Mall (2026).

Bernoulli’s Principle dictates that as the velocity of a fluid increases, its static pressure decreases(Pilot Mail,2026). By placing the airfoil at the chimney exit, External wind is forced to accelerate over the curved surface creating a localized low pressure zone at the exit of the exhaust pulling out air actively. This constriction based pressure drop is known as the venturi effect(Pilot Mail,2026) This makes the flow of air from the chimney laminar and eliminates any possibility of boundary layer separation and backflow, while increasing the time at which air leaves the chamber. Transforming this prototype into a highly efficient self regulating ventilation system.

VI. Conclusion

The development of this airfoil assisted design improves standard ventilation systems and demonstrates the tangible benefits of applying aerospace

engineering principles to residential structures. The optimized prototype demonstrates a clear performance margin over traditional design providing significant increase of efficiency and eliminating drawbacks that come with the traditional design.

Future considerations : Future iterations will focus on integrating a self-orienting mechanism, inspired by wind vane mechanisms to ensure that the venturi effect remains constant with shifting wind directions ensuring adequate performance in different environmental conditions. This would allow the prototype to be an adaptive, self regulating building component maintaining peak ventilation efficiency.

VII. References

Above All. (2026). *Minimize the Stack Effect*. Above All Winnipeg Insulation. <https://aboveallinsulation.net/>

Understanding Bernoulli's Principle: Key Concepts Explained.
<https://www.pilotmall.com/blogs/news/understanding-bernoullis-principle-key-concepts-explained>